

Teaching with CLARIN: Insights and Recommendations from the 2026 University Curricula Workshop

Report

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This report summarises the key discussions, findings, and recommendations from the CLARIN in University Curricula Workshop, held in Utrecht on 21–22 April 2026. Attended by 30 participants from 20 European countries, including educators, researchers with teaching duties, and representatives of CLARIN BoD, User Involvement and Knowledge Infrastructure Committees, the event explored how CLARIN’s language resources, tools, and infrastructure can be meaningfully integrated into university teaching across disciplines.

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1. Context and Objectives

CLARIN ERIC (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure) is a pan-European research infrastructure dedicated to making language data and tools accessible for research, education, and public benefit. While CLARIN has grown significantly as a research infrastructure, its uptake in university teaching remains uneven, and teachers would benefit from greater support from CLARIN ERIC, their national consortia, and their university administrations.

This report summarises the discussions, presentations, and outcomes of the [CLARIN in University Curricula workshop](#), held over two days, 21-22 April 2026, in Utrecht, the Netherlands. The workshop continued the strategic process initiated at the [CLARIN@Universities workshop in 2019](#) and further discussed during the CLARIN Cafés: [How to use CLARIN in \(online\) Higher Education](#) (2020) and [Towards guidelines for integrating CLARIN into Teaching](#) (2021). The 2026 edition was framed by the [CLARIN ERIC Strategy 2024-2026](#), and focused specifically on how national consortia and CLARIN ERIC can work together to enhance CLARIN's visibility at universities and meet the teaching needs of diverse disciplines, including *linguistics, digital humanities, language technology, speech and NLP, as well as social sciences, history, and literary studies*.

The aim of the workshop was twofold:

- 1) Showcase how CLARIN services, tools, and teaching resources available throughout the distributed infrastructures are meaningfully integrated into university teaching across language-related disciplines and discuss current challenges and needs.
- 2) Strengthen the collaboration across institutions and disciplines by encouraging the participants to co-design reusable teaching materials, curriculum models, and community-oriented resources to support the long-term integration of CLARIN into higher education curricula and teaching.

2. Who Attended

The workshop brought together 30 participants from 20 European countries, representing a significantly more diverse group than the equivalent 2019 event. Participants included university lecturers, assistant professors, programme coordinators, training officers, and PhD researchers with teaching duties, as well as members of the CLARIN Board of Directors, and representatives of the User Involvement and Knowledge Infrastructure Committee.

Countries	Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Greece, Iceland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia, Sweden, and the United Kingdom
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Teaching levels	Primarily Master's and Bachelor's level, with a few participants teaching at the doctoral level
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Disciplines	Linguistics, Digital Humanities, Language Technology, Speech & NLP, Translation, Terminology & Interpreting Studies, Corpus Linguistics, Data Stewardship, Literary & Media Studies, etc.
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3. What the Pre-Workshop Survey Revealed

A pre-workshop survey¹ provided a baseline understanding of participants' current practices and needs. Key findings included:

3.1 Awareness vs. Use

While awareness of CLARIN services was relatively widespread, systematic pedagogical use remained inconsistent. Educators were more familiar with their national CLARIN consortium offerings than with the services and resources maintained by the central hub, such as the Virtual Language Observatory, Switchboard, the Virtual Collections Registry, and the Learning Hub. Several participants were aware of the services but unsure how to integrate them into their courses.

3.2 How CLARIN is Used in Teaching

Where integration does occur, it is typically modular rather than course-wide, introduced through a single lecture, assignment, or student project. The most common pedagogical activities included searching CLARIN collections, working with language data, and annotating digital resources. More advanced practices, such as data depositing and applying FAIR data principles, tend to occur at Master's and PhD levels.

¹ The full analysis will be published soon.

3.3 Main Barriers

The main barriers identified by the workshop participants for integrating CLARIN-related content into their curricula are:

- Lack of space in the curriculum
- Limited instructor time to learn CLARIN tools
- Insufficient institutional support
- Difficulty finding relevant, language-specific examples
- Shortage of ready-to-use, adaptable teaching materials that could be used across disciplines
- Students' and teachers' limited technical skills

"The challenges are both practical and structural, highlighting the need for more accessible teaching materials, institutional support and time-efficient ways for instructors to engage with CLARIN." – Pre-workshop survey summary

3.4 What Educators Need Most

Respondents were clear about their priorities:

- Ready-to-use datasets linked to real research scenarios
- Adaptable slide decks and sample lesson plans
- Student-oriented tutorials for self-paced learning
- Recorded tutorials and train-the-trainer sessions
- Better discoverability of materials in the CLARIN Learning Hub

The results of the pre-workshop survey were used to design the workshop programme and identify topics for the group discussions. The programme committee considers disseminating a slightly-adapted version of the survey to the wider community of teachers and educators across CLARIN.

4. Key Themes from the Workshop

The workshop opened with a presentation by [Darja Fišer](#), the CLARIN ERIC Executive Director, who situated CLARIN within the wider European research infrastructure ecosystem, focusing on the [Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud](#) (SSHOC) landscape. The presentation highlighted the three SSHOC strategic pillars: data, tools and workflows (including development of the SSH Open Marketplace and potential integration into the EOSC Federation); training and education (centred on the SSH Competence Centre); and advocacy and outreach across key European bodies.

The [SSH Open Marketplace](#) was highlighted as a key shared resource built on contextualisation, curation, and community, while the [SSH Competence Centre](#) was presented as a cross-ERIC initiative supporting open data, interoperability, and collaboration across SSH communities, with sustainability and AI exploration among its stated priorities.

The opening talk was followed by two keynote presentations, eleven lightning talks, and two group discussions. This section summarises the key themes cutting across disciplinary boundaries and institutional contexts.

4.1 Curriculum Integration: Understanding the System

Keynote speaker [Vesna Lušicky](#) (University of Vienna) opened the workshop with a talk titled “What Is a Curriculum, Really? Aligning Curriculum Realities with CLARIN Integration” ([Slides](#)). Vesna highlighted how rapid technological and societal change is reshaping higher education, placing both educators and students in an environment of ongoing transformation.

Drawing on Taba’s (1962)² definition of curriculum as a “planned course of learning,” Vesna stressed that a curriculum represents a structured framework encompassing intentions, content, teaching methods, learning outcomes, and assessment practices. Educators frequently introduce new content, including CLARIN-related material, without first establishing a clear rationale for why students should learn it. This disconnect between educational objectives and CLARIN services was identified as a central barrier to meaningful integration. Vesna introduced a **five-level model of curriculum formation** (supra, macro, meso, micro, and nano levels), noting that individual lecturers often operate primarily at the nano level. Formally embedding CLARIN within official curricula is therefore challenging, as CLARIN does not function as an established academic discipline. She also distinguished between the **official curriculum** (formal

² Taba, H. (1962). Curriculum development: Theory and practice. Harcourt Brace & World.

learning outcomes, module descriptions, institutional regulations) and the **hidden curriculum** (implicit assumptions, values, and priorities), emphasising that practical teaching decisions are often influenced by institutional constraints, funding pressures, student numbers, and personal beliefs.

Key message: CLARIN integration must never be an add-on. It must serve defined learning objectives and be embedded where it genuinely fits.

4.1 Teaching NLP and Data Skills in the Age of AI

Generative AI and large language models (LLMs) dominated much of the workshop’s discussion. Keynote speaker [Barbara McGillivray](#) (King’s College London) opened Day 2 with a presentation on “AI, Open Data, and the Future of Language Research Teaching” ([Slides](#)), in which she named AI “the elephant in the room” in contemporary language education.

Barbara described many current students as a “generation of button-pushers”, learners who routinely use AI tools but uncritically, lacking the foundational skills to evaluate sources, assess data quality, or reproduce research workflows. A central theme of her talk was the contrast between FAIR data principles and the realities of LLM training corpora. Barbara argued that while making language data technically accessible is straightforward, ensuring it is truly reusable is substantially more demanding, and it is precisely where CLARIN’s distinctive value lies. She proposed repositioning CLARIN as a pedagogical foundation for teaching responsible research practice.

Participants agreed that CLARIN is particularly well-positioned to address this challenge. Unlike LLM training corpora, CLARIN resources are curated, documented, licensed, and structured, embodying the FAIR data principles required for reproducible research. The SSH Open Marketplace was identified as a valuable catalogue for contextualising data resources by linking them to related workflows, publications and training materials.

This seems to be a “generation of button-pushers”, users who deploy AI tools habitually but uncritically – Barbara McGillivray (King’s College London)

The subsequent presentations on the topic and group discussions reinforced this theme. The Language Technology and NLP group noted that while LLMs have transformed student expectations, educators still have a responsibility to teach the reasoning behind traditional NLP pipelines, including when and why automated systems fail. Prompt engineering and critical evaluation of AI outputs were identified as urgent new competencies.

4.3 Data Literacy as a Core Competency

Across sessions, participants returned consistently to the theme of data literacy. Topics such as data citation, research data management (RDM), metadata quality, source criticism, GDPR compliance, and FAIR data principles were identified as essential academic skills rather than optional ones. Mietta Lennes highlighted the importance of teaching students to cite data as a standard research practice, while Helene Andreassen discussed RDM training needs among PhD students. Both highlighted that existing RDM university training courses are often too generic and insufficiently tailored to linguistics and language-related disciplines.

4.4 Disciplinary Diversity and the Need for Tailored Examples

One of the most consistent messages across all five breakout groups was the need for discipline-specific examples and problem-driven entry points. Across Linguistics, Translation Studies, Digital Humanities, Data Stewardship, and Language Technology, participants agreed that abstract descriptions of CLARIN's infrastructure are rarely convincing to students or to sceptical colleagues. What works is starting with a concrete research question students already understand and showing how CLARIN can help answer it, ideally with minimal technical jargon.

*"Start from a 'study' problem that students understand and show how CLARIN can help solve it."
— Group 5 (DH and Humanities)*

5. Presentations: Strategies, Practices, and Emerging Technologies

Over both days, participants delivered two sets of lightning talks covering the curriculum strategies, data literacy practices, and the integration of AI into language teaching. The following summaries capture the key contributions.

5.1 Strategies for Integrating CLARIN into University Curricula

How to Make CLARIN Visible Beyond One-Course Level by Communicating with University Authorities by Jurgita Vaičėnonienė | [Slides](#)

Jurgita Vaičėnonienė (CLARIN-LT) presented a curriculum-wide approach developed for an Erasmus Mundus Joint Master's application, in which CLARIN-related content was systematically woven throughout the programme using a gradual "build-up" model. The approach introduces CLARIN concepts progressively, from foundational awareness in early stages to advanced practical application at the MA level, with particular emphasis on CLARIN's multilingual and cross-national corpus support.

“Formally communicating CLARIN’s institutional value to administrators, not just to students, is essential for long-term recognition and sustainability.” - Jurgita Vaičėnienė

Connecting Teaching, Thesis Work, and Resource Creation by Katerina Frantzi | [Slides](#)

Katerina Frantzi (University of the Aegean) presented a model from the University of the Aegean that links student thesis work directly to resource creation, supporting engagement with the full data lifecycle from corpus building to repository deposit. The model has been applied across undergraduate and postgraduate programmes in areas including linguistics, archaeology, and language teaching. Discussion raised a *widely shared challenge*: the quality of student-generated outputs does not always meet CLARIN repository standards, and universities rarely have mechanisms in place to sustain, maintain, or reuse these outputs over time.

Teaching with CLARIN: FAIR Data and Open Science in Humanities Curricula by Iulianna van der Lek & Maja Miličević Petrovic | [Slides](#)

Drawing on the [UPSKILLS project](#) and teaching experience at the University of Bologna, Iulianna van der Lek (CLARIN ERIC) introduced a curriculum framework that tailors learning objectives to academic level, showing how CLARIN can serve as a pedagogical tool for integrating Open Science, FAIR data principles, and Research Data Management into humanities programmes. The key argument was that shifting from abstract policy to situated, practice-oriented learning, CLARIN enables students to engage with authentic language data and professional workflows throughout the research data lifecycle.

RDM Training for PhD Students by Helene N. Andreassen | [Slides](#)

Helene N. Andreassen (UiT The Arctic University of Norway) surveyed the Research Data Management needs of PhD students and early-career researchers, identifying recurring challenges: not knowing where to find support, navigating GDPR and institutional ethics requirements, and resistance to data sharing in some research cultures. A common problem is that existing training is too generic, not tailored to disciplinary contexts. She presented the [DocEnhance Data Stewardship](#) course as a reusable and adaptable resource, and called for closer collaboration between research communities and RDM specialists. During the discussion, Christoph Draxler highlighted that RDM support is especially critical at two career stages: proposal writing and project completion. Iulianna noted that good (research) data management practices and skills can be valuable at every level, not only for PhD students.

Data Citation in Research and Teaching by Mietta Lennes | [Slides](#)

Mietta Lennes (University of Helsinki) argued that data citation is a foundational academic skill, closely aligned with CLARIN's mission and essential for research transparency and reproducibility. Citation practices are not impartial; what is cited and when reflects disciplinary norms and values. Data citation remains underdeveloped in many research communities, and source criticism is insufficiently addressed in education. While many repositories auto-generate citation instructions from metadata, inconsistencies arise when metadata is harvested across systems. *Recommendations* included developing a CLARIN resource of citation examples and best practices, and improving metadata quality and consistency across repositories.

Navigating GDPR, Licensing and Ethics for Language Data by Henk van den Heuvel | [Slides](#)

For many humanities educators, the legal and ethical layer of data-driven research is a significant barrier. Henk van den Heuvel (CLARIN BoD, Radboud University) presented a practical toolkit for teachers to help students navigate licensing, ethics, and GDPR when working with sensitive language resources. Key points included the importance of understanding the legal bases for processing personal data, the risks of relying on consent (it can be withdrawn at any time), and the case for Public Interest as a more stable basis for research use. *Key take*: the institution's legal department should be involved/consulted from the very start of data collection.

Finding and Reusing Open Educational Resources by Thalassia Kontino & Giulia Pedonese | [Slides](#)

This bridging presentation provided participants with an overview of existing training catalogues and repositories, including the [CLARIN Learning Hub](#), [H2IOSC Training Platform](#), and the [SSH Open Marketplace](#), with emphasis on discoverability, adaptation, licensing, and reuse. Thalassia Kontino (CLARIN ERIC) presented the recently launched [CLARIN Learning Resources Catalogue](#) and demonstrated how learning resources on various topics, developed by lecturers and trainers within the community, can be browsed using available metadata and filters. Giulia Pedonese (CNR-ILC & CLARIN-IT) introduced the H2IOSC Training Platform and showed examples of how open CLARIN courses were adapted to serve the learning needs of other target audiences. The presentation highlighted that CLARIN training materials should be treated as FAIR objects, assigned a persistent identifier, and made citable, reusable, and adaptable to encourage broader sharing of teaching practices. A key institutional barrier is university resistance to including CLARIN topics in formal student assessment, which needs to be actively addressed. There is also a question about CLARIN's positioning relative to the growing trend toward micro-credential courses, which warrants further exploration.

Browse the [CLARIN Learning Resources Catalogue](#) to see examples of courses in which CLARIN tools and services are used in teaching. To propose a new resource, email training@clarin.eu or upload your resource to the [CLARIN Community on Zenodo](#).

5.2 Emerging Practices, Platforms, and Technologies in Teaching

Teaching Prompt Engineering for Humanists by Federico Boschetti | [Slides](#)

Federico Boschetti (CNR-ILC & CLARIN-IT) presented prompt engineering as an emerging literacy for humanists, a skill at the intersection of interpretation, formalisation, and interaction with AI systems. His teaching approach moves students progressively from naive prompting to structured, reproducible, and critically informed practice. Effective prompt engineering reduces hallucinations through explicit constraints, source grounding, and verification. *The CLARIN K-centre network was proposed as a potential didactic infrastructure for prompt engineering, and a new type of CLARIN resource was envisioned: documented prompts linked to resources, best practices, and evaluation results.*

Integrating LLMs in Corpus-Related Courses by Florian Kunneman | [Slides](#)

Florian Kunneman (University of Utrecht) shared practical examples from his teaching in both data science and language science curricula, where LLMs are now a standard means of corpus analysis. He focused on the design of data annotation and fine-tuning assignments and on the practical issues that arise, including constraints on GPU availability at the university level. Google Colab was presented as a workable solution, though not unlimited. He also raised *the need for a safe, institutionally hosted infrastructure where students can experiment with LLMs without dependence on commercial platforms.*

Corpora and AI in Linguistic Tasks: Idiomaticity by Petya Osenova | [Slides](#)

Petya Osenova (Sofia University) demonstrated how large corpora and corpus management tools (e.g., NoSketch concordance) can be successfully combined with AI prompts (e.g., ChatGPT 3.5 or Gemini) to explore the meaning and distribution of idiomatic expressions. The case study used [CLASSLA-web.bg 2.0](#) (Bulgarian Web) from the CLARIN CLASSLA K-centre, alongside ChatGPT, to test the capabilities of corpora and AI in performing various tasks on South Slavic languages relevant to linguists, lexicographers, philology students, and language users. The presentation illustrated a goal-oriented, problem-driven approach: *rather than teaching tools in the abstract, evaluation tasks provide a concrete pedagogical setting in which students critically assess AI outputs.*

LLMs in Linguistics Teaching: A User-Centred Lexicographic Approach by Ana Salgado | [Slides](#)

Ana Salgado (University of Porto) presented an approach to introducing LLMs into linguistics teaching through lexicographic practice, anchored in real user needs rather than technology-first framing. The case study drew on ongoing work integrating the Dictionary of the Portuguese Language of the Lisbon Academy of Sciences into [Evaristo.ai](#), a Portuguese chatbot made available via PORTULAN CLARIN. The presentation argued for treating LLMs not as substitutes for reliable reference sources such as dictionaries, but as interfaces for accessing curated information. This approach helps students develop a more nuanced understanding of AI capabilities and limitations.

6. Insights from Breakout Discussions

This section presents the insights from the two breakout discussions organised during the workshop.

6.1 Discipline-Specific Insights

During the first breakout session, participants worked in thematic groups to identify realistic pathways for integrating CLARIN at the course, programme, faculty, and university network levels. Participants were grouped by expertise to ensure discussions reflected the diversity of disciplinary backgrounds and teaching contexts represented at the workshop. This structure enabled participants to exchange concrete examples, share best practices, and discuss discipline-specific approaches to CLARIN integration across a wide range of areas.

6.1.1 Language Technology, NLP, Computer & Information Sciences

This group focused on the challenge of teaching foundational NLP methods at a time when LLMs appear to make them redundant. The group felt CLARIN integration is most realistic at the MA level and above, where students can engage actively with data and tools.

Key barriers identified:

- Non-technical students struggle to understand foundational needs such as lemmatization without practical grounding.
- Students tend to bypass structured learning by asking LLMs directly for solutions.
- Policies for the appropriate use of advanced automatic technologies are often unclear.

Priority recommendations:

- Develop a teaching resource educating on prompt engineering strategies
- Strengthen CLARIN's role as a benchmark data provider, making resources directly usable in evaluation platforms.
- Improve tooling to allow direct use of CLARIN resources with simple, one-liner Python commands (comparable to HuggingFace).
- Pursue collaboration agreements with [European AI Factories](#) to use CLARIN resources directly within HPC centres.

6.1.2 Linguistics, Language Studies & Corpus Linguistics

This group identified a wide range of existing courses as natural entry points for CLARIN, from Corpus Linguistics and Discourse Analysis to Research Methods, Sociolinguistics, and BA/MA seminars on data management. The participants stressed that when research questions drive the design of teaching materials,, CLARIN fits naturally into most linguistics courses.

Key barriers identified:

- Educators are often unaware of CLARIN resources or may use them without knowing they are CLARIN-branded tools.
- Educators' fear of technical complexity and lack of time to prepare.
- The risk of students finding CLARIN repetitive if introduced across too many courses without variation
- Anglo-centric bias in available resources and examples; teaching materials cannot always be reused or translated.

Priority recommendations:

- Establish CLARIN coordinators at each university, with sub-coordinators in different disciplines.
- Provide regular training for teachers and ready-made, adaptable slide decks.
- Developing a self-deposit system for multilingual materials and translated teaching examples.

6.1.3 Translation & Interpreting, Terminology & Lexicography

The group highlighted that student cohorts in translation and interpreting often share only one common language, requiring a greater emphasis on methodology and processes rather than content. Topics identified as natural entry points included machine translation evaluation, terminology work, and lexicography.

Key barriers identified:

- Lack of discipline-specific CLARIN modules for translation and interpreting contexts.
- Insufficient localisation of resources and examples for diverse language backgrounds.

Priority recommendations:

- Develop discipline-specific CLARIN modules for translation, terminology, and lexicography.
- Create an accessible entry point (website, forum) for these communities to share examples and start collaborative discussions.
- Organise a kick-off workshop to build community and establish shared resources.

6.1.4 Data Stewardship

The group identified data stewards and librarians as a critically underused yet strategically important audience for CLARIN. They argued that data stewards should function as a key bridge between discipline-specific researchers and CLARIN infrastructure, but currently lack discipline-specific knowledge to fulfil this role effectively.

Key barriers identified:

- Tension between depositing in institutional repositories versus CLARIN repositories, which should be presented as complementary rather than competing.
- Many data stewards are not specialists in linguistics or language research.
- The perception of data stewardship as an additional workload rather than an integral part of the research method.
- Difficulty reaching senior researchers and supervisors.

Priority recommendations:

- Engage data stewards as first points of contact and driving forces for outreach to teachers and researchers.
- Develop an activity based on the [Re3data](#) registry to enable students to compare repositories by data type (e.g., as a role-play or group exercise).
- Adapt CLARIN promotional materials specifically for data stewards.
- Reuse basic shared modules and build discipline-oriented layers on top of them, rather than developing from scratch.

The group also announced the forthcoming STARDAST project, launching in September, an opportunity to build a data stewardship network with expertise in CLARIN-related disciplines.

6.1.5 Digital Humanities, Literary Studies & Media Studies

This group offered some of the workshop's most candid observations about the barriers to integration in non-technical humanities environments. CLARIN was described as having “acted like a missionary in the Humanities”, enthusiastic but sometimes inaccessible.

Key barriers identified:

- CLARIN is perceived as too technical and acronym-heavy in non-technical environments.
- Promotional materials are discouraging for non-technical audiences.
- It is unclear to many educators who to contact for integration support.
- Significant differences in institutional organisation across countries.

Priority recommendations:

- Develop a new family of “teaching-fit” resources: small, modular datasets in standard formats, paired with processing tools and evaluation gold standards.
- Raise awareness through discipline-specific, problem-driven research questions and technological solutions, using as little technical jargon as possible.
- Encourage students to deposit resources and take ownership through problem-based learning.
- Extend action to the meso and macro levels, not just classroom-level integration, engaging university libraries and teaching and learning centres as entry points.
- Pursue “evangelism” through national consortia: tailored lectures, tutorials, and road shows for individual courses and programmes.

"Good infrastructure is invisible and tends to be most visible when it breaks down. It is not crucial that lecturers and students are not aware of using CLARIN resources, as long as they use them." – Group 5

7. Co-Designed Community Outputs

The second day's breakout session shifted from diagnosis to action, with four groups working to co-produce reusable community resources.

7.1 Revised CLARIN Toolkit for Lecturers

Group A drafted a blueprint for an updated version of the [CLARIN Trainers' Toolkit](#), specifically adapted for university lecturers. Key design principles included:

- Granularity over packaging: break content into small, independently downloadable units rather than large bundles
- Template-first design: structure slides to give lessons shape, not just content
- Link use cases directly to curated datasets from the Virtual Collection Registry
- Include Zotero bibliographies in multiple citation formats (including BibTeX)
- Provide an exercise bank with assignments, quizzes, and roleplay scripts
- Add localisation examples with step-by-step documentation for adapting materials to national contexts.

7.2 Communication Pack for University Alliances

Group B explored opportunities for collaboration with European University Alliances, including Transform4Europe, ERUA, CIRCLE-U, and EUTOPIA. Key recommendations included:

- Map all 73 European University Alliances and filter those with missions most aligned with CLARIN's strengths in language, multilingualism, and open science
- Develop a formal communication pack positioning CLARIN as a partner for internationalisation, mobility, and cross-border data projects
- Leverage the Erasmus Teacher Mobility programme to connect CLARIN trainers with alliance member universities
- Establish a joint working group to define priority areas for cooperation.

The ResiLiANG project, submitted under Horizon WIDERA, bringing together Vytautas Magnus University, Saarland University, and the University of Alicante, was presented as a concrete proof-of-concept model for this type of collaboration.

7.3 Classroom-Friendly Infrastructure

Group C defined criteria and priorities for making CLARIN resources more pedagogically usable. Key recommendations included:

- Resources should be problem-oriented, not just resource-oriented, searchable by research question, not only by tool or data type.
- Metadata must be sufficient for students to evaluate whether a corpus is appropriate for their task.
- Quality evaluation frameworks are needed to help students critically assess tools and datasets.
- CLARIN should communicate more clearly about hardware requirements and the availability of AI factory infrastructure for teaching.
- Classroom slides demonstrating CLARIN use should be shared as low-cost, high-impact resources.

7.4 Reusable Teaching and Learning Objects

Group D reviewed existing course designs and discussed principles for reusable, modular teaching materials. Key outcomes included:

- A “switchboard” concept for course development: modular subtask building blocks that educators can combine and localise
- Courses should be developed with both student-facing and teacher-facing versions; train-the-trainer materials are essential
- Short video introductions (circa 3 minutes) were proposed as scalable entry points for both students and educators
- Localisation in terms of language and disciplinary context is essential, not optional
- CLARIN materials should reduce the workload for teachers, not add to it.

8. Recommendations

The challenges identified throughout the workshop do not have a single solution, nor a single owner. Sustainable integration of CLARIN into university teaching requires action at every level, from infrastructure policy to individual classroom decisions. The recommendations below reflect that shared responsibility.

8.1 For CLARIN ERIC and National Consortia

- Develop a revised Lecturers' Toolkit with granular, independently usable components, curated use cases, localisation guidance, and exercise banks.
- Build and maintain a Virtual Collection Registry dedicated to teaching, linking curated datasets to documented use cases and learning objectives.
- Strengthen CLARIN's positioning as a benchmark data provider and make datasets directly accessible via standard APIs (comparable to Hugging Face).
- Map European University Alliances and develop targeted communication materials and partnership proposals for the most aligned alliances.
- Create a network of university-level CLARIN coordinators and discipline-specific sub-coordinators to provide local support and peer-to-peer knowledge sharing.
- Develop and publish success stories of CLARIN integration at the course, programme, and institutional level.
- Launch train-the-trainer workshops, hosted at national consortia, focused on specific tools, disciplines, and teaching contexts.
- Broaden outreach to include university libraries and teaching and learning centres as institutional entry points, not only individual lecturers.

8.2 For Universities and Programme Designers

- Treat data literacy, including data citation, RDM, source criticism, and FAIR practices, as a core academic competency, not an optional extra.
- Explore meso-level integration by including explicit references to digital skills and research infrastructures in official programme documentation.
- Connect students with CLARIN through thesis work and research projects, allowing them to contribute to and deposit reusable language resources in the CLARIN repositories.
- Engage data stewards and librarians as active partners in curriculum development, not only as support staff.

8.3 For Individual Educators

- Identify the level at which you can act within your curriculum structure, and start there, even at the nano level.

- Use discipline-specific, problem-driven examples that begin with a research question your students already care about.
- Use CLARIN as a source of authentic, curated data to teach the critical evaluation of AI-generated outputs.
- Share teaching materials openly via [CLARIN Community on Zenodo](#)³ or the [CLARIN Learning Resources Catalogue](#)⁴, however small or preliminary.
- Connect with local CLARIN consortium contacts for support, examples, and localisation assistance

9. Next Steps

The workshop concluded with a discussion of follow-up actions. Participants agreed on the following priorities:

- A community discussion paper drawing on the workshop findings, open to broader contributions from the CLARIN community and targeted at a peer-reviewed journal.
- Formation of a task group to develop and maintain the revised Lecturers' Toolkit.
- A pilot train-the-trainer workshop series at the national consortium level, focused on specific tools and disciplines.
- A mapping exercise for European University Alliances to identify the strongest candidates for formal cooperation.

Interested in contributing? Contact Iulianna van der Lek, the CLARIN training officer at training@clarin.eu.

³ As the CLARIN Learning Resource Catalogue is not a repository, Zenodo can be used to publish training materials and tutorials from CLARIN-funded events, workshops and summer schools. The CLARIN Community on Zenodo has a curation procedure in place. For instructions how to submit, see: <https://www.clarin.eu/content/adding-new-training-resource-clarin-zenodo-community>.

⁴ If your learning resource is already published in open access but not yet available in the catalogue, please email the URL at training@clarin.eu and it will be included.

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- Jurgita Vaičenonienė (KIC)
- Maria Gavriilidou (UIC)
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- Tanja Wissik (NCF)
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For the full programme, slide decks, and session recordings, see:
clarin.eu/event/2026/clarin-university-curricula-workshop.